

D3.1: Business models for Federated e-Infrastructures

Deliverable

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Abstract

This document presents a way to categorise different arrangements of federations in the e-Infrastructure domain and looks at the business models that these arrangement imply. This includes developing some simple tools to assist in this process.

Table of Contents

Abstract	1
Table of Contents	2
1. Introduction	4
1.1. Contribution to project objective	4
1.2. Structure of the deliverable	5
2. Features and purpose of business models.....	6
3. Methodology.....	7
3.1. Approach	7
3.2. Actors.....	7
3.3. Selection of federation types	8
4. Tools.....	8
4.1. FedSM Federation Responsibility Model.....	8
5. Business model template	11
5.1. General description	11
5.2. FedSM Business Model Canvas	12
6. Business model 1: Invisible coordination.....	13
6.1. General description	13
6.2. Implications of the federation type.....	15
6.3. Business model canvas	16
6.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.	17
6.4.1. Federation members	17
6.4.2. Consumers.....	17
7. Business model 2: Advisor	17
7.1. General description	17
7.2. Implications of the federation type.....	19
7.3. Business model canvas	20
7.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.	21
7.4.1. Federation members	21
7.4.2. Consumers.....	21
8. Business model 3: Matchmaker	21
8.1. General description	21
8.2. Implications of the federation type.....	23

8.3.	Business model canvas	24
8.4.	Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.....	25
8.4.1.	Federation members	25
8.4.2.	Consumers	25
9.	Business model 4: One Stop Shop.....	25
9.1.	General description	25
9.2.	Implications of the federation type.....	27
9.3.	Business model canvas	28
9.4.	Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.....	29
9.4.1.	Federation members	29
9.4.2.	Consumers	29
10.	Business model 5: Integrator.....	29
10.1.	General description	29
10.2.	Implications of the federation type.....	32
10.3.	Business model canvas	33
10.4.	Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.....	34
10.4.1.	Federation members	34
10.4.2.	Consumers	34
11.	Conclusions.....	34
12.	Version History	35

1. Introduction

The European e-Infrastructure landscape began through cooperation between academic institutions, and this cooperation generally remained informal or undocumented as the services developed, partly as it facilitated cooperation in the academic sphere by reducing administrative complexity. As these e-Infrastructures have matured there has been a need for more explicit and formal collaboration, leading to the formation of various governance and cooperation structures. These structures, having grown organically, are not always clear, and having a broader view of the possible arrangements of actors and the implications of this is desirable.

We regard the general type of structure these e-Infrastructures have formed as a sort of federation – by which we mean a collection of at least partially autonomous entities that act together in some manner to provide a consumer with services. This federation includes a central federator, whose role will vary widely depending on the type of federation considered, from strong central control through to weak coordination or even internal support for the federation and its members.

This document provides a framework for looking at different varieties of federated e-Infrastructures, and seeing how the various forms of federation impact or define their business models. For FedSM this is necessary as different forms of federation imply different 'locations' for service management processes. That is to say, in tightly bound, centralised federations the federator will likely also have to take on service management responsibility. If they only provide limited services then the service management may be carried out more directly by federation members who deal directly with customers.

In this document we identify a general way of assessing federation types and examine business models for a set of arrangements that cover those seen or imagined for current e-Infrastructures.

1.1. Contribution to project objective

D3.1 acts as an important input to many other deliverables in work packages 3-6. It is not the direct basis of other work packages but will be used to help interpret them in different situations. For instance, D3.2 – the minimum requirements for federated e-Infrastructure will be implemented in different ways based on the federation model that is being considered. A centrally controlled federation will perform service management at the federation level, with the federator responsible for incident management, problem management and other ITSM processes. If the federator provides some promotional or light brokering services they will likely implement a lesser subset of the ITSM processes to be described in D3.2.

This will lead to differences in the D3.3, the first stage implementation plan, as the understanding of the kinds of federation that each client partner represents will affect which minimum requirements they need to meet. Inevitably this will then influence the second

stage implementation plan (D3.4) and the good practice guide (D3.5), where we imagine advice will be given per federation type.

Similarly, the role map in D4.1 will be used differently based on the kind of federation in question, as the roles will be distributed differently between the federation and suppliers. It will also influence later deliverables in work package 4 that relate to the professional certification scheme, as in designing this scheme it will be important to cover topics in service management that will be needed in common federation types.

Work in work packaged 5 and 6 will be influenced as the baseline maturity will again be related to the federation type, which will suggest the processes and technologies under discussion.

Figure 1: D3.1 in the context of key project deliverables

1.2. Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable begins by considering the general features of business models, and the methodologies and tools used by FedSM to categorise and understand them. Following this,

these are applied to five kinds of federation, and the results discussed. Finally, conclusions are given.

2. Features and purpose of business models

According to Amit & Zott, a business model depicts “the content, structure and governance of transactions designed so as to create value through the exploitation of business opportunities.”¹ In this context, value should not be limited to economic value in terms of financial income or return on investment; social, cultural or other forms of value may also be taken into account.

In the context of federated e-Infrastructures, being aware of the value proposition mechanism in a specific scenario may be vital for understanding the purpose of the federation is and how it works. It will also be needed to understand the role of services and service management – and how value is created or supported through services as well as how these services need to be managed.

As a concrete example, assume the federation is a number of resource providers connected and organised in a national Grid infrastructure. The federator is an organisation (body) responsible for “coordinating” the overall Grid with its services (e.g., computing) for virtual organisations (VOs). In this simple example, there are at least two types of services: first, the service(s) provided by “the Grid” as a whole towards its VOs; second, the services provided by the federator – supporting the main Grid service(s). For the services provided by the federator, many different general models may exist, and there are numerous parameters according to which the actual role and connected tasks of the federator can be defined. Thus, the question to be addressed is: What does “coordination” mean in this context? For example, is it the responsibility of the federator to coordinate the resolution of incidents related to Grid resources and act as a single point of contact in this context for a VO? Or will the VO contact the respective resource provider directly?

All this depends on understanding a federator’s business model, related services as well as the way(s) in which value is created for “customers” and value creation is supported by other involved parties. Thus, in order to think about service management in federated e-Infrastructures, we need to approach different possible business models first. Otherwise, general assumptions would have to be made which most likely are not valid in many real-world cases.

Our requirements on a business model can be summarized as follows:

- A business model should provide a clear idea of the value that is created by a federator in its specific federation context.
- A business model should draw a clear picture of the stakeholders involved besides the federator; this shall include any types of relevant partners contributing to the value proposition as well as “consumers”.

¹ Amit, R., and Zott, C.,(2001), “Value creation in e-business,” *Strategic Management Journal*, 22, pp. 493-520

- A business model should highlight the most important relationships in the regarded federation context, i.e. relationships and dependencies between the involved parties.
- A business model should cover information about resources required to deliver value as well as the (physical or logical) channels through which service and value is delivered.
- Any business model should be clearly defined in scope distinguished from other business models.

3. Methodology

In order to state the business models we must first define a loose methodology for selecting business models and define the different types of actors we consider.

3.1. Approach

The goal of this document is to provide an understanding of the different ways that federated e-Infrastructures can operate. The goal is not to describe every possible option (there would be too many) or simply to describe what happens today, but to create an open framework for describing and understanding different kinds of federation.

In order to do this we have defined a minimal set of actors, and developed a model for understanding how types of federation vary. Some of these exist in today's e-Infrastructure landscape while others are new.

Having created a system for looking at federation types we identify a few that are of interest as they are in use or planned, we then described the implications for the business model in each case. As such one could consider the models as 'business model templates' rather than actual models.

3.2. Actors

This document seeks to provide quite a broad level of understanding of federation types and business models, so we have selected a minimal set of actors to consider.

- The **consumer** – the 'customer' of the overall federation and the group that benefits from the main service type that the federation offers. In a multi-cloud computing federation this would be someone wanting cloud computing services (processing, storage etc.) from the federation.
- The **Federation members**, a heterogeneous group of organisations or bodies that come together to form a federation, whether a loose or tightly bound one. The majority of these will likely be providers of the main service type - in the case of a multi-cloud they will be commercial or private cloud operators. However there may be other members of the federation that supply supporting technical services, perhaps web portals, AAI systems or other facilitating systems.
- The **Federator** is a body that provides some value-added services that somehow relate to the whole federation. These can range from very abstract or high level services such as advising customers on their needs, through fully integrated

federated service providers that essentially take over all contact with customers and conceal the federation.

3.3. Selection of federation types

We have selected five types of federation to describe, and for which we provide business models. In doing so we tried to select a range of types of federation, from incredibly lightweight to fully integrated. These are types of federation that are in use or being considered by e-Infrastructure organizations, though in some cases stated in terms they may not initially recognise. We feel they give a good initial range of options, though of course more detail could be added, as other kinds of federation or variants of those shown here (for instance in the 'one-stop shop' model incident and problem management may or may not be federated).

We also note that despite trying to provide a range of options, in only one of them are service management processes split, in others they tend to sit with either the federator or remain with the members (perhaps implying and federation would happen on the consumer level). However, these models will be further developed through the project in dealing with the real federations that are client partners in FedSM.

4. Tools

To facilitate the analysis and categorisation here we have developed two tools, one adapted from an existing tool and the other new. The FedSM Federation Responsibility Model and the FedSM Business Model Canvas.

4.1. FedSM Federation Responsibility Model

The purpose of the FedSM Federation Responsibility Model is to provide a quick and simple view of how responsibility is assigned within federations acting together to provide services. We will use the example of a multi-Cloud computing federation for illustration.

The Responsibility Model provides a list of processes, components and activities down the centre, responsibility for which are assigned to one of three groups: the consumer, the federation members or the federator.

Each item on the Responsibility Model can be coloured one of three ways.

- Red if it is the responsibility of the federation members. In this case the activity is likely to not be coordinated, rather carried out separately by each federation member as they need.
- Blue if the federation takes on the coordinated implementation of the activity, such that the consumer sees the coherent output and does not have to be concerned about the federated activities behind them.
- Green are activities which are not coordinated by the Federator, but the consumer needs to be coordinated so must do so themselves.

The activities listed on the Responsibility Model are separated into four areas.

- Service management processes are the management processes associated with providing the main service type of the federation, such as Cloud computing services in our example.
- Consumer-facing services/components are activities that address or benefit the consumer, and which they will always be aware of
- Federation-member facing services are those where 'customers' are federation members.
- Supporting service components are technical services that might facilitate the overall federation of the main service type, for instance some shared AAI system or portal.

The Federation Responsibility Model is released under a Creative Commons 3.0 Attribution licence² (CC BY 3.0).

² See <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/> for license text.

[Colour items to that of the federator or Federation members to indicate responsibility]

5. Business model template

For FedSM we have chosen a fairly simple method for recording business models, one that is visual and should make immediate sense to community members. This is important, as members of the community need to see their own activities in the models, rather than perhaps seeing them as something commercial and unfamiliar.

We have selected the Business Model Canvas³ a simple and popular representation of business models, as the basis for our work. We have adapted business model canvas (which is released under a creative commons licence v 3.0) to better fit federated e-Infrastructures. Other than phrasing and terminology this is largely to allow for models not based on direct payment. As such cost structures become cost and resource use models, and revenue streams becomes support (incorporating revenue streams but also in-kind contributions. The project will accordingly release this revised template under a creative commons v3.0 license.

The model begins with a general description to provide some context. This is followed by the canvas, which is divided into relatively self-explanatory sections to be filled in (and includes guidance notes). If multiple consumers are envisaged they are coloured differently in the upper right section, and other sections where the answer varies depending on consumer are coloured in the same way. These are shown in the following sections

5.1. General description

Name: [name of entity whose business model is described]

General description: [General features in prose terms]

Real world possible or actual example: [What real or imagined entity might have this model. Choose examples familiar to the community you address.]

³ See <http://www.businessmodelgeneration.com/canvas>

5.2. FedSM Business Model Canvas

[Name]				
Key partners (Input) <i>[Who do you work with, who supplies you with what you need to provide your service, what do they provide]</i> Text	Key activities <i>[What key activities do you need in order to provide the service]</i> Text	Value proposition (what do you offer) <i>[What value do you deliver to the customer? What problems do you solve? What needs are you satisfying? What bundles are you offering]</i> Text	Consumer relationships <i>[What relationship do you have with your user communities – both current and expected future relationships]</i> Text	Consumer segments (Output) <i>[Who do we create value for? What kind of group are they (mass, niche, etc.)]</i> Text
	Key resources <i>[What resources do we need to provide the service]</i> Text		Channels <i>[How do you reach your customers? How effective and costly are they?]</i> Text	
Cost and resource use models <i>[What costs do you have to provide the service (real financial or effort, use of existing hardware etc.)? How predictable are they? Do your models scale?]</i> Text			Support (revenue streams or other support) <i>[How do you fund the provision of this service (direct usage fee, state support)? How will this change in future? Who will provide funding? How do you demonstrate value for national/EU funding?]</i> Text	

6. Business model 1: Invisible coordination

6.1. General description

Name: Invisible coordination

General description:

This kind of federator works with federation members only (not with consumers) by giving them the support and/or technology that enables some level of light federation.

Additionally, it can certify federation members against some set of requirements, to enable them to advertise or confirm some sufficient range and level of services.

This is an extreme example of federator, in that minimal federating activities are carried out, and from the consumer point of view they deal only with individual federation members. However, this still encourages use of federated resources, for instance enabling standard end-points by each provider. It also encourages consumers to see federation members as relating to one another in some manner, but despite this no technical service elements will be provided by the federator in this case.

It is quite likely that in e-Infrastructures this role may be combined with other federation models, such that invisible coordination is one of several services offered by a federator.

Real world possible or actual example:

Certification authority – assesses businesses in meeting requirements related to a specific standard e.g. ISO 9001.

Franchise – a federator acts here like franchisor, that “owns” some know-how and technology on how to operate in some specific manner; franchisee are the providers that set-up special access services, based on knowledge and technology provided by federator, that enable federated use of their resources. A common branding would be used, but all interaction takes place with the specifically contacted franchise. For example, McDonald’s franchises.

Guild or union – provides certificate for trading some goods in particular area or a represents workers in an industry.

Consumer
[consumer of main service type federation offers]

6.2. Implications of the federation type

As we have mentioned, this type is a rather extreme case of federator with minimal cooperation between federation members and little added value. The resulting “invisible coordination” can be regarded as more enabling federation-readiness among the providers than providing a real federation. Some other interactions between providers need to be undertaken to build truly integrated/federated services.

On the other hand, by unifying, or at least standardizing, technical and managerial interfaces, “Invisible coordination” could make more in depth federation much simpler. In the most advanced scenarios, the “federated” providers will be ready to federate themselves ad-hoc based on their customers needs and their business goals as a result of standardization achieved through the invisible coordination. Federation procedures and tools might be, in such a scenario, subject of standardization and certification by an “invisible coordinator”.

In conclusion, “Invisible coordination” can build any kind of federation, however this federation will be very loose or if not must be united by some other body, that might be a member (or group of them), customer or other type of federator that would be included in parallel to the invisible coordination scenario.

6.3. Business model canvas

Federation Model: Invisible coordination				
<p>Key partners (Input) <i>[Who do you work with, who supplies you with what you need to provide your service, what do they provide]</i></p> <p>Resource owners (provide the thing which is federated)</p> <p>Federation technology providers</p> <p>Providers of software and services that support the federation of resources.</p>	<p>Key activities <i>[What key activities do you need in order to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing or selecting federation technology and gathers related know-how - Acts as certification authority for providers - Maintain publicly available repository of certified providers 	<p>Value proposition to customer (what do you offer) <i>[What value do you deliver to the customer? What problems do you solve? What needs are you satisfying? What bundles are you offering]</i></p> <p>Enable usage from customers whose needs cannot be satisfied by a single site and who are skilful enough to adapt to federated model/technology.</p>	<p>Consumer relationships <i>[What relationship do you have with your user communities – both current and expected future relationships]</i></p> <p>(Dedicated) personal assistance, documentation</p> <hr/> <p>Channels <i>[How do you reach your customers? How effective and costly are they?]</i></p> <p>Face to face contact, Web portal, technical white-papers, technology demos,</p>	<p>Consumer segments (Output) <i>[Who do we create value for? What kind of group are they (mass, niche, etc)]</i></p> <p>Resource owners (thing that is federated)</p>
<p>Cost and resource use models <i>[What costs do you have to provide the service (real financial or effort, use of existing hardware etc)? How predictable are they? Do your models scale?]</i></p> <p>Staff costs (technical support, certification auditors)</p> <p>Technological research</p>		<p>Support (revenue streams or other support) <i>[How do you fund the provision of this service (direct usage fee, state support)? How will this change in future? Who will provide funding? How do you demonstrate value for national/EU funding?]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Public funding, to provide national/EU added value (impact shown through researcher performance, opportunities) - subscription from resource owners - In-kind contributions from resource owners 		

6.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models. .

6.4.1. Federation members

In case of members that provide service for federation, the general business model does not change comparing to non-federated model. All the activities towards consumers remain the same. However, some of the technologies used or supplied by members might come through federator that approves them, making them common for the federation. Provision of services might be supported by external monitoring and might require some alteration to meet federator requirements. Those are the cost of enabling new customers that need federated services.

Members that provide support services for the federation need to communicate with the federator, who needs certify their solutions and the service providers that actually operate them. In this model, marketing activities of support service suppliers should be focused on the federator, while support activities are focused on members that are providers of the main service type.

6.4.2. Consumers

As this kind of federator has no direct contact with consumers it does not modify their business model directly. However, it enables standardized communication and technical interfaces that are common between many federation members. Through this, the consumer can benefit from savings on maintaining their applications.

7. Business model 2: Advisor

7.1. General description

Name: Advisor

General description:

A set of experts in the area of e-Infrastructures that leverage this expertise to advise research communities on how to understand their needs for computing services and how they can make effective strategic choices and select a suitable provider.

Real world possible or actual example:

Similar to the EC-sponsored IPR helpdesk or an advice bureau/resource centre.

7.2. Implications of the federation type

In this federation model, the consumer is well-aware of the federator on the one hand, since the advisor is visible to the consumer – which is a main difference compared to the invisible coordination federation type. On the other hand, the consumer is (or should be) aware of the very limited role of the federator in the service delivery context. Activities of the federator are focused on advice and promotion, taking place before and during the service is provided. In the actual service delivery context, the advisor takes over no significant responsibility.

As a consequence, no service management capabilities need to be in place on the advisor side, if this business model type is applied strictly without any changes or extended duties or responsibilities of the integrator. Thus, the federation members cannot rely on any service management-related support through the federator.

The value of the federator here is their knowledge of the federation members, which facilitates the selection of members to serve consumer needs, or makes the members more accessible or attractive. Whether this is sufficient added value to balance the expense of the advice (whether funded directly or indirectly) depends on the complexity of the service offerings of the members. We might say that in an ideal world service offerings from members would be so clear that advice would not be necessary, but given the complex and heterogeneous nature of e-Infrastructures, this is unlikely in the foreseeable future.

As with invisible coordination, it is quite possible that a real federator may combine this type of action with others as different service offerings to consumers, which may also make for better added value overall for those consumers using the federator.

D3.1: Business models for Federated e-Infrastructures

7.3. Business model canvas

Federation Model: Advisor				
<p>Key partners (Input) <i>[Who do you work with, who supplies you with what you need to provide your service, what do they provide]</i></p> <p>Resource owners (provide information about their services).</p>	<p>Key activities <i>[What key activities do you need in order to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Online and personal advice service -Marketing 	<p>Value proposition to customer (what do you offer) <i>[What value do you deliver to the customer? What problems do you solve? What needs are you satisfying? What bundles are you offering]</i></p> <p>Expert advice on how to meet community IT service needs through access to e-Infrastructures. Advice that helps researchers understand how their day-to-day needs translate into needs that an e-Infrastructure provider can fulfil.</p> <p>Better educated customer base, more able to express their needs (technical and managerial) and therefore more likely to understand your offering and be satisfied with it.</p>	<p>Consumer relationships <i>[What relationship do you have with your user communities – both current and expected future relationships]</i></p> <p>Personal assistance and self-service. May use both in parallel.</p> <p>Automatic (scrape service data) or self-service (submit data to federator). Personal assistance possible initially and for periodic review.</p>	<p>Consumer segments (Output) <i>[Who do we create value for? What kind of group are they (mass, niche, etc)]</i></p> <p>Research communities</p> <p>e-Infrastructure service providers (resource owners, smaller federations).</p>
	<p>Key resources <i>[What resources do we need to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Platform for consumers to get information -Expertise in understanding research needs - MetaCatalogue of all resource owners' services 		<p>Channels <i>[How do you reach your customers? How effective and costly are they?]</i></p> <p>Online via web portal for most contact, face to face contact (direct and via conferences etc.) for initial contact or complex situations.</p> <p>Face to face possible for initial contact/reviews. Otherwise web portal and technical interfaces.</p>	
<p>Cost and resource use models <i>[What costs do you have to provide the service (real financial or effort, use of existing hardware etc)? How predictable are they? Do your models scale?]</i></p> <p>Staff costs for experts and platform operation</p> <p>Knowledge platform (s/w, h/w, network etc.)</p>		<p>Support (revenue streams or other support) <i>[How do you fund the provision of this service(direct usage fee, state support)? How will this change in future? Who will provide funding? How do you demonstrate value for national/EU funding?]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Public funding, to provide national/EU added value in helping researchers choose appropriate e-Infrastructures. - Fees for advice services from researchers / subscription from service providers for listing them. - In-kind contributions from service providers. 		

7.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.

7.4.1. Federation members

The business models of federation members are not markedly affected by the existence of an advisor-type federator, except as a marketing channel. The information required by the advisor about the members should be publically available, and the additional load to support the advisor will be largely just ensuring they have the information required to give positive advice about a service. It is possible if the advisor has a high enough profile then the members may pay a subscription to be listed in their pool of possible resources for recommendation, but this will likely be a relatively minor cost in comparison to usage fees for their services, and may even be based on referral commissions (though this will jeopardise the independence of the advice).

All other elements of the member business models will be unaffected, as they will still need to manage relationships in other senses in the same way as they would as a provider outside the context of the federation.

7.4.2. Consumers

Consumer business models will be equally affected quite minimally by the existence of an advisor. The advisor will act in a pre-sales capacity with regard to the services consumed, and will simplify the steps needed to define key activities and select key partners. Again, any costs incurred for the advice will likely be minimal compared to the cost of the services consumed.

8. Business model 3: Matchmaker

8.1. General description

Name: Matchmaker

General description:

In the 'Matchmaker' model, the federator manages resource allocation in some way. The customer discusses requirements and receives a resource allocation from the federator valid for one or more resource providers. The contractual agreement and the financial transactions are handled directly between the customer and resource provider. The federator generates revenues from the resource providers in the form of percentage on transactions or membership fee. This model is more suitable for customers who need access to many resource providers. While this same set of functions could be carried out in a non-federated environment the difference here is that the federation means that rather than helping the consumer make a choice of service provider they allow the matchmaker to make the selection, based on their knowledge and existing interaction with federation members.

Real world possible or actual example:

Kayak.com. You find all the relevant information that you are looking for based on a set of criteria (e.g., flight departure, destination, times), but are redirected directly to the resource provider.

8.2. Implications of the federation type

The matchmaker model differs from the advisor in one key area, which is around the allocation of resources. All service management is still handled by the federation members, however, there is a difference in how the federator is perceived by consumers in comparison to models where the federator only gives advice. To a greater extent the reputation of the federator will be driven by the effectiveness of the resources they assign to consumers.

In order to provide this shared service, processes need to be standardised across the federation, at least enough for rational comparisons to be made in selecting members to fulfil consumer needs. This might involve the federation members agreeing to common processes such as centralised monitoring and accounting, methods of request review and selection and validation criteria.

Customers will still need to interact with multiple service providers in terms of formalising agreements, but the provision of resources will be viewed as more central, professional, and easier to understand, therefore, easier to use. However, this also suggests that there will be a benefit to standardised monitoring and billing systems amongst members, as if a consumer must learn multiple different systems to make use of the services from each provider, then the more united impressions from the federator may be lost.

D3.1: Business models for Federated e-Infrastructures

8.3. Business model canvas

Federation Model: Matchmaker				
<p>Key partners (Input) <i>[Who do you work with, who supplies you with what you need to provide your service, what do they provide]</i></p> <p>Resource owners (provide the thing which is federated)</p> <p>Technology Providers (software and services that support the federation of resources)</p> <p>Business Partners (alliances for wide range of collaborative activities)</p>	<p>Key activities <i>[What key activities do you need in order to provide the service]</i></p> <p>-Coordination/CRM (personal and/or online) -Marketing -Assign federation members (and their resources) to customers.</p>	<p>Value proposition to customer (what do you offer) <i>[What value do you deliver to the customer? What problems do you solve? What needs are you satisfying? What bundles are you offering]</i></p> <p>Single point of contact for information discovery based on specific requirements for best cost to service comparisons with facilitated customer-to-provider relationship.</p> <p>Increased promotion of services, more targeted customers with a well-defined demand and shared overhead costs and customer relations management.</p>	<p>Consumer relationships <i>[What relationship do you have with your user communities – both current and expected future relationships]</i></p> <p>Personal assistance and self-service. Dedicated personal assistance, supported by automated service</p> <p>Channels <i>[How do you reach your customers? How effective and costly are they?]</i></p> <p>-Social Media -Web portal -Virtual Meetings -Face-to-face contact</p> <p>-Face to face contact -Web portal -Technical interfaces</p>	<p>Consumer segments (Output) <i>[Who do we create value for? What kind of group are they (mass, niche, etc.)]</i></p> <p>-Researchers -Research Communities</p> <p>-Resource owners -Technology Providers -Business Partners</p>
<p>Cost and resource use models <i>[What costs do you have to provide the service (real financial or effort, use of existing hardware etc)? How predictable are they? Do your models scale?]</i></p> <p>-Staff costs {including support or not} -Knowledge platform (s/w, h/w, network etc.) -External costs for software and services to support federation</p>		<p>Support (revenue streams or other support) <i>[How do you fund the provision of this service (direct usage fee, state support)? How will this change in future? Who will provide funding? How do you demonstrate value for national/EU funding?]</i></p> <p>-Public funding, to provide national/EU added value (impact shown through researcher performance, opportunities)</p> <p>- Commission on money from researchers - Subscription from resource owners - In-kind contributions from resource owners</p>		

8.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.

8.4.1. Federation members

In the Matchmaker model, relevant federation members can be classified in 3 important categories: Resource owners to provide the computing, data, and storage resources to be federated; Technology Providers to deliver the software and services that support the federation of resources; Business Partners to forge alliances for a wide range of collaborative activities that do not fall within the direct provider/customer relationship or transaction.

The Matchmaker model offers several advantages for the federation members such as an increase in promotion of services by using a single organization with market knowledge, established relations, tools and resources and broader reach of prospective clients. This allows for better opportunities to receive more targeted customers as well as focused feedback and requirements from potential customers through the use of a central expert, in this case the federator. One of the most important aspects within the Matchmaker model is cost. By using a federator, members can share/reduce overheads and customer relationship management. However, some level of control needs to be conceded over service delivery in order to receive the added benefits. The matchmaker model offers a balanced approach regarding overall control and Return on Investment (RoI).

8.4.2. Consumers

One of the most important aspects to consider will be the impact on consumers, both advantages and disadvantages. The Matchmaker model will allow consumers to find the best solution available on the market by having direct contact with a single organization for information discovery and eventually for resource allocation from a technical perspective. However, contracts, agreements and financial transactions will need to be done directly with each member, therefore depending on the number of sites and services, this could lead to the establishment and management of a number of different relationships. This level of complexity will determine the experience and level of satisfaction by the consumer.

9. Business model 4: One Stop Shop

9.1. General description

Name: One Stop Shop

General description:

A single point of contact that lets a research community discuss their needs, negotiate service level agreements, sign contracts and make payments. Despite dealing largely with the federator, the service itself it provides by federation members.

Real world possible or actual example:

A code-share agreement between airlines. Though you deal with one company for searching flights, booking, making payments etc., you travel on the plane of another company.

D3.1: Business models for Federated e-Infrastructures

9.2. Implications of the federation type

One stop shops are unusual in as much as the customer experiences almost entirely contact with the federator, while in fact the majority of activities remain carried out in an uncoordinated way by the federation members.

From the consumer point of view, they deal initially and mostly with the federator. The federator gives them advice, helps understand their requirements and then selects resources and closes contracts, legal agreements and bills, however the federation members provide the service itself.

Within the federation, the federator is providing a service that brings in customers for its members, and validates them as providing a service of some agreed upon service quality. However, the federator does not act for the members in others ways such as mediation, communication or collective bargaining.

In terms of service management, responsibility will end up being split. By virtue of being a 'one stop shop' the federator must have the ability to practice service level management to agree SLAs with consumers, budgeting and accounting to provide a price, and service reporting to provide coherent reports across the federated service.

However they will not carry out other service management processes such as capacity management, as ultimately the federation member or members selected to provide the actual main service must be the ones ensuring they have sufficient capacity. Equally, change management will not be federated as members are not tied into a single cohesive whole in this example. While we suggest that incident and problem management will not be federated, it could be in some cases.

While from the consumer point of view this seems to be a relatively simple way to deal with a service, it does not benefit from the cohesiveness of a fully integrated federation. Some management processes must be federated but the split between those that are and those that are not is complex and may incur higher costs (or at least no cost savings) within the federation or make failure more likely.

One might suggest that such a federation is good while working effectively but is likely to be worse than others when there is a major issue. Even if incident management is federated problem, management will likely not be, so it will be harder to track the problems underlying incidents and orchestrating changes to fix them. Likewise, if a problem actually results from the interaction or joint usage of service components from several members it will be difficult for the federator to arrange it being fixed.

D3.1: Business models for Federated e-Infrastructures

9.3. Business model canvas

Federation Model: One stop shop				
<p>Key partners (Input) <i>[Who do you work with, who supplies you with what you need to provide your service, what do they provide]</i></p> <p>Resource owners (provide the thing which is federated)</p> <p>Providers of software and services that support the federation of resources.</p>	<p>Key activities <i>[What key activities do you need in order to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Managing platform for users -Agreement/contract development and monitoring -Financial agreements and transactions -Marketing 	<p>Value proposition to customer (what do you offer) <i>[What value do you deliver to the customer? What problems do you solve? What needs are you satisfying? What bundles are you offering]</i></p> <p>Single point of contact to understand your needs, see opportunities to fulfil them, understand cost and contracts, and make agreements.</p> <p>Does not provide the service directly but the service support {goes through the federator/goes to the person supplying the service}.</p> <p>Easy access to customers to consume your resources and generate more income or show greater impact of those resources. Minimise overhead to attract and manage agreements with customers.</p>	<p>Consumer relationships <i>[What relationship do you have with your user communities – both current and expected future relationships]</i></p> <p>Transition from personal assistance to automated service over lifetime (Dedicated) personal assistance, supported by automated service</p>	<p>Consumer segments (Output) <i>[Who do we create value for? What kind of group are they (mass, niche, etc)]</i></p> <p>Research communities</p> <p>Resource owners (thing that is federated)</p>
	<p>Key resources <i>[What resources do we need to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Single platform for customer interaction -Expertise in matching research needs to resources - MetaCatalogue of all resource owners' services 		<p>Channels <i>[How do you reach your customers? How effective and costly are they?]</i></p> <p>Face to face contact (both direct and via conferences etc) Web portal Technical interfaces (APIs etc) Face to face contact (both direct and via conferences etc) Web portal Technical interfaces (APIs etc), personal contact to support staff.</p>	
<p>Cost and resource use models <i>[What costs do you have to provide the service (real financial or effort, use of existing hardware etc)? How predictable are they? Do your models scale?]</i></p> <p>Staff costs {including support or not}</p> <p>External costs for software and services to support federation</p> <p>Potential centralised platform for customer interaction (s/w, h/w, network etc.)</p>		<p>Support (revenue streams or other support) <i>[How do you fund the provision of this service (direct usage fee, state support)? How will this change in future? Who will provide funding? How do you demonstrate value for national/EU funding?]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Public funding, to provide national/EU added value (impact shown through researcher performance, opportunities) - Commission on money from researchers / subscription from resource owners - In-kind contributions from resource owners 		

9.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.

9.4.1. Federation members

Federation members in a “One Stop shop” scenario will come in two types, those owning computing resources to be federated, and those providing support services that enable federation.

For providers of computing services (to be federated) the one stop shop simplifies their business model with regards to the federation as all ‘sales’ and administrative contact is with the federator. However it does not restrict them to accessing consumers only via the federation – they will retain a quite generalized value proposition. As the federation takes on the additional work of organizing consumers via the federation, the resource owner can continue to serve other consumers in the way it did prior to the federation with little impact on its day to day activities. Depending on the situation they can also view the federator as a customer of their consulting services, reselling them to end users, or a provider of marketing and administration services. This will likely depend on demand and funding sources.

For those providing support services for the federation, the federation business model will directly shape their business model. If the ‘one stop shop’ is the only federator it is quite possible they will be dependent on this federator as a single client. For a ‘one stop shop; style federation their value proposition will be highly tailored and forced to integrate with other suppliers and existing rules and structures within the federation.

9.4.2. Consumers

A “one stop shop” makes for quite a simple business model among consumers. A one-stop shop offers the flexibility of multiple providers but the simplicity of a single point of contact. Trust in the one stop shop will be key, but if it can be maintained the relationship will be a close one based on personal contact backed up with automatic and self service systems for day to day management.

10. Business model 5: Integrator

10.1. General description

Name: Integrator

General description:

The federator serves as a single point of contact for operations as well as contractual concerns to the research communities. The research community can discuss their needs, negotiate a service level agreement and have the service provided by a single partner.

The federator takes responsibility for the service provisioning, even though it does not own the provided resources, save for resources for managing the service such as access and monitoring systems. The federated resource owners are seen as suppliers / sub-providers by the federator. Contractual obligations exist between the federator (integrator) and the

research community customers, as well as between the federator and the resource owners, but not between the research community and the resource owners directly.

Real world possible or actual example:

Virtual mobile phone operators that do not own any network infrastructure, yet act as service providers to their customers.

Consumer
[consumer of main service type federation offers]

Federator Integrator (Coordinated action)	Service Management processes (for main federation service type)	Federation members (Uncoordinated action)
	Design & transition of new or changed services Service Level management (SLAs, OLAs) Service reporting Service continuity & availability management	
	Financial management (budgeting, accounting, charging) for services	
	Capacity management	
	Information security management	
	Incident & service request management	
	Problem management Configuration management Change management	
	Release & deployment management	
	Continual service improvement	
	Consumer-facing services/components	
	Provision of main technical service	
	Advice	
	Assignment of resources	
	Legal contracts	
	Billing and payments	
	Platform for using service	
	Federation-member facing services/components	
	Internal communication	
	Collective bargaining	
	Internal mediation	
	Promotion	
	Validation	
	Facilitate technical interoperation	
	Supporting service components (technical)	
General split of support components:		

10.2. Implications of the federation type

In the Integrator model, the consumer is dealing with a single provider and each federation member (resource owner or supplier of support services) is dealing with a single customer, which in both cases is the federator / integrator.

The federator handles all complexity arising from the federated nature of the service provisioning. While the resource owners need to manage only their own resources and services, the federator is responsible for managing the federated service in all aspects. The federated nature of the service is largely opaque (i.e. invisible) for both the consumer and the resource owners.

This arrangement offers to greatest added value to the federation, but is also the closest to a traditional commercial model of service provision, where standard ITSM can be used. The difference is likely that the agreements within the federation may not be the same as those seen in a commercial supply chain.

10.3. Business model canvas

Federation Model: Integrator				
<p>Key partners (Input) <i>[Who do you work with, who supplies you with what you need to provide your service, what do they provide]</i></p> <p>Resource owners (provide the thing which is federated)</p> <p>Providers of software and services that support the federation of resources.</p>	<p>Key activities <i>[What key activities do you need in order to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Managing services, i.e. running a complete SMS (Service Management System) -Managing agreements/contracts with the resource owners (Supplier Management) -Building a service catalogue based on resource owner capabilities 	<p>Value proposition to customer (what do you offer) <i>[What value do you deliver to the customer? What problems do you solve? What needs are you satisfying? What bundles are you offering]</i></p> <p>Single point of contact to understand your needs, see opportunities to fulfil them, understand cost, contracts, make agreements and provide services.</p> <p>Easy access to customers to consume your resources and generate more income or show greater impact of those resources. Minimise overhead to attract and manage agreements with customers.</p>	<p>Consumer relationships <i>[What relationship do you have with your user communities – both current and expected future relationships]</i></p> <p>Transition from personal assistance to automated service over lifetime (Partnership in the context of Supplier Management)</p>	<p>Consumer segments (Output) <i>[Who do we create value for? What kind of group are they (mass, niche, etc)]</i></p> <p>Research communities</p> <p>Resource owners (thing that is federated)</p>
	<p>Key resources <i>[What resources do we need to provide the service]</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Single platform for customer interaction -Identity, access and usage accounting system - Catalogue of all services - Catalogue of all resource owners' (sub-)services 		<p>Channels <i>[How do you reach your customers? How effective and costly are they?]</i></p> <p>Face to face contact (both direct and via conferences etc) Web portal Technical interfaces (APIs etc) Face to face contact (both direct and via conferences etc) Web portal Technical interfaces (APIs etc)</p>	
<p>Cost and resource use models <i>[What costs do you have to provide the service (real financial or effort, use of existing hardware etc)? How predictable are they? Do your models scale?]</i></p> <p>Staff costs {for service management, support, administration etc.}</p> <p>External costs for software and services to support federation</p> <p>Centralised platform (s/w, h/w, network etc.)</p> <p>Payments to resource owners</p>			<p>Support (revenue streams or other support) <i>[How do you fund the provision of this service (direct usage fee, state support)? How will this change in future? Who will provide funding? How do you demonstrate value for national/EU funding?]</i></p> <p>-Public funding, to provide national/EU added value (impact shown through researcher performance, opportunities)</p> <p>- Money from researchers</p>	

10.4. Considerations for federation member and consumer business models.

10.4.1. Federation members

As in the One Stop Shop business model, members can have the role of a resource provider or provider of services supporting the federation. However, from the viewpoints of these members, the Integrator can be regarded as a (contracted) customer, and the Integrator's customers or consumers are invisible for the suppliers. Thus, a traditional supply and value chain is built up where each part of the chain knows his direct neighbour rather than being involved in any relationships with parties or stakeholders beyond this.

10.4.2. Consumers

From the consumer perspective, an Integrator is a full service provider throwing the federation and everything inside it into shadow. Thus, in a consumer's business model, the Integrator is regarded as a supplier of services with no other responsibility for the service delivery to be taken by the consumers themselves.

11. Conclusions

Here we describe a methodology for considering types of federation and the business models they imply. Through this we seek to reduce the complexity of the federated e-Infrastructure domain enough to allow for further discussion and comparison of business models, and a better understanding of how these require different approaches to service management.

The federation Responsibility Model divides up the activities and processes that might make up a federation, and has been filled in various ways to reflect kinds of federation seen today, or imagined, though many other ways to fill it in are possible. These not only give the 'shape' of the federation but indicate the likely location of responsibility for service management processes, such that they assist organisations in understanding what service management must be federated and what will remain the responsibility of federation members.

For each example federation type we provide an outline business model using an adaption of the Business Model Canvas, a simple way to portray the basic elements of a business model. While we can see similarities between the business models, their differences match well to some of the confusions seen in the current e-Infrastructure landscape as to what a federator should or can do.

We also note that current federators are unlikely to fit simple one federator type. Rather different services within their portfolio or different areas of activity are using or will use different models. This has likely contributed to difficulties in defining business models for current federators, as members of the community have tried to find single descriptions for what are actually complex or composite service providers. Rather we suggest breaking down their service portfolio and looking on a case-by-case basis at which services obey which models.

This work will also form the basis for later deliverables as it will be necessary to understand which federation type is in play in determining what elements of service management a federator must take on. For instance an Advisor has little need for service management other than for some sort of advice platform, whereas an integrator must take on the full service management load in dealing with customers. Apart from general advice this approach will be used to look at the client infrastructures in the FedSM project, such that they can see in which areas they need to implement ITSM processes.

12. Version History

Version	Date	Author	Change record
0.1	17.10.2012	O. Appleton	Skeleton
0.2	4.11.2012	O Appleton	Assignments
0.3	15.11.2012	O. Appleton	Semi-complete draft
0.5	21.11.2012	T. Schaaf	Adding missing parts
0.6	21.11.2012	O. Appleton	Complete draft
0.7	26.11.2012	O. Appleton	Changing to scorecard
0.8	28.11.2012	O. Appleton	Adding scorecards, general revision and improvement
0.9	30.11.2012	L. Alves	Revision
1.0	30.11.2012	O. Appleton	Finalising
1.1	11.02.2014	O. Appleton	Corrections